

Benz_10perc_1218

Sample Name **Benz_10perc_1218**
Date collected **2025-12-18**

Pulse sequence **PROTON**
Solvent **d2o**

Temperature **28.5**
Spectrometer **varian300.chem.byu.edu-inova300**
Study owner **marsh81**

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SAMPLE	wet	n
<hr/>		
date	Dec 18 2025	SPECIAL
solvent	d2o	
file	/opt/nmrdata/mars	temp
h81/Benz_10perc_1218_20		28.5
251218_01/PROTON_08.fid		gain
		30
		spin
		0
		hst
		0.008
		pw90
		11.500
ACQUISITION	alfa	10.000
<hr/>		
sw	4799.6	FLAGS
at	3.414	
np	32768	il
fb	3000	n
bs	32	in
ss	4	nw
d1	20.000	dp
nt	8	y
ct	8	hs
		nn
		PROCESSING
		lb
		0.50
TRANSMITTER		fn
		131072
<hr/>		
tn	H1	DISPLAY
sfrq	299.972	
tof	300.0	sp
tpwr	56	-599.9
pw	3.833	wp
		4799.5
		rfl
		600.0
		rfp
		0
DECOUPLER		rp
		-66.6
		lp
		21.5
<hr/>		
dn	C13	PLOT
dof	0	
dm	nnn	wc
decwave	W40_pfgAuSW	234
dpwr	28	sc
dmf	26316	8
		vs
		2024
		th
		44
PRESATURATION	ai	cdc
		ph
<hr/>		
satmode	n	
Plotname:	PROTON_08_plot03--	